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- Source 1 URL: https://web.facebook.com/eventsofovercomer/?_rdc=1&_rdr
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- Source 3 Description: This is the google location of this religious group.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There are other religious groups in cultural contact with this religious group. People from different religious groups are often seen in the different services conducted by this religious group. They often have Igbos, Yorubas and other cultural groups in attendance.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Despite being majorly a Yoruba-speaking religious group, this religious group accommodates other cultures. There are different people of different cultures who are very active in the religious group.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The religious group is not neutral when it comes to the matter of its culture. Though it strongly upholds its Christian values it does not force those of the religious other to accept its religious views. It engages with them and seeks to persuade and convince to see things from their perspective.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There are no violent conflicts within the sample region. Every culture is permitted and are not discriminated against.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There is no violent conflict whatsoever with groups outside the sample region. They live in peace and harmony with both members and non-members alike.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: When children are born to parents who are members of the group, such children are

automatically counted as members until they grow up and decide otherwise.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The personal choice of individuals to identify with the group is always respected. No one is ever conscripted by force into the group.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: The religious group is open to people of different classes. However, the current membership is made up of people from the lower class of the society.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no specific age grade for one to become a member of this religious group.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: The group does not practice gender discrimination. It allows both males and females to exercise their freewill to become members.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The only ritual performed by intending member of this religious group is to accept Jesus Christ and to make a declaration for this act.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: This is in accordance with the Biblical dictate of the Great Commission that gives this religious group the mandate to go therefore and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all that they have been commanded. This group go about preaching to convert both Christians (those not of the same church) and non-Christians alike. Apart from this, one particular tool being used by this religious group is healing. They claim to heal peoples' illnesses and once this is done, the healed would join the group.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: This is just in the fulfilment of the Great Commission mandate as espoused in this religious group's holy scripture (the Bible)

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: It is not all adherents that go out on missionary work. They have specific people assigned for this mandate, which is often a thing of choice.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Proselytisation is never coercive. It is all about persuasion. Most of its members usually become members by seeking for spiritual help.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: This religious group is not supported by any political group. There is no political party in power

that gives state support to this religious group. It is a religious group that does not receive government support.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that when any member departs from the faith, they have backslidden. Such fellow can however be reinstated when they acknowledge their error and return to the beliefs of the group.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: There is no persecution or punishment whatsoever for apostates. This is because there is freedom of thought or opinion and any member can have different opinion from that of the religious group.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 5000

Reference: ALUKO, Oluwasegun Peter, and Adenike Oluwabukola IREYOMI. "Colour Symbolism in a Nigerian Church: The Case of Prophet/evangelist Abiodun Oladele of the Overcomers" *Evangelical Ministries International (ori-oke Asegun)* 04, no. 11 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2020.41102>.

Reference: Media, Overcomers. "Events at Overcomers Chapel Ori-oke Asegun Ajebamdele Ileife". Accessed December 25, 2023. <https://web.facebook.com/eventsofovercomer>.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 3

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: This group is founded and actively directed by a single leader (Apostle Abiodun Oladele), who is the prophet and apostle in charge. As the founder and general overseer of this religious group, he permits others to also act in the capacity of leaders in the religious group, especially in the branches of the religious group.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: This group is founded and actively directed by Apostle Abiodun Oladele, who is the founder, general overseer, prophet and apostle in charge. This leader permits others to also act in the capacity of leaders in the religious group, especially in the branches of the religious group.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Since there are different branches of the religious group, there are different leaders stationed in these branches. These leaders do not have any hierarchy among themselves.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Since there are different branches of the religious group, there are different leaders stationed in these branches. These leaders oversee these different branches and are known for their acts.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: In an interview with the leader of this religious group (Apostle Abiodun Oladele), it was revealed that his acquisition of power was as a result of his encounter with the Holy Spirit in the dream. He claimed that he was in a bush (which is the present site of the headquarters of the ministry) praying and fasting for three months. While in this bush, he encountered many situations that called for the exercising of the power of God on his life, which eventually led to his supernatural enablement.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Though the church leader is assumed to be fallible because he is human. However, his members do not frivolously accuse him of fallibility because of the love and respect they have for him.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Many of the followers or disciples of a religious leader are not required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Since this is a Christian religious group, they obviously uphold the use of the Christian Holy Scripture known as the Bible.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: All Scripture is God-breathed and is useful for teaching, rebuking, correcting, and training in righteousness, so that the servant of God may be thoroughly equipped for every good work (2 Timothy 3:16-17).

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Spirit is claimed to have inspired the men of old to have written the Scriptures

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Non-divine human beings are believed to have written and compiled the Scripture together, as they have been inspired.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The scriptures have already been transmitted to the language the people understand

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The bible has been canonised and made up of 66 books. 39 of these books are in the Old Testament portion of the scriptures and 27 in the New Testament

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage: 55
 - Notes: This religious group has two very large buildings that could be regarded as monumental architectures.
- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - Square meters: 300
- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 26
- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - Height, square meters: 10
- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 15
- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Percentage of area: 65

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

- ↳ Tombs:
 - No
- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - No
- ↳ Temples:
 - No
- ↳ Altars:
 - Yes
- ↳ Devotional markers:
 - No
- ↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
 - Yes [specify]: Bookshop, Prayer House

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

— Yes

Notes: This religious group believes just as most Christians that at death, the soul is separated from the body and survives in a conscious or unconscious disembodied state, but on the future Day of Judgment souls will be re-embodied (whether in their former but now transfigured earthly bodies or in new resurrection bodies) and will live eternally in the heavenly kingdom. Despite the fact that this religious group is majorly dominated by the Yoruba and with the knowledge of the Yoruba culture, this spirit-body distinction is clearly stated and in line with the major Christian belief.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

— Yes

Notes: This religious group believes that their spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts. Coupled with the fact that this religious group is mostly dominated by the Yoruba ethnic group, they believe the spirit and the mind possess unique powers and properties that are quite different from every other body part.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

— Yes

Notes: This religious group believes that the spirit-mind is non-material. The group believes that the spirit and the body are two separate entities that are quite distinct from each other, though they are fused together into one to form the human being.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

— Yes [specify]: This religious organisation believes that the spirit and the body are two distinct entities that interact with one another. They believe that God created both the spirit and the body for His glory and that they are inextricably linked to their well-being, labour and ministry, worship or devotion to God, and, ultimately, God's redemption.

Belief in afterlife:

— Yes

Notes: This religious group believes in the resurrection of the body on the Day of Judgement, a time when God will judge everyone individually and they will be sent to either heaven or hell, depending on their deeds on earth.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

— Yes

Notes: This religious group believes the spatial location of the afterlife is up there in heaven. They often use the Yoruba word "Orun" to qualify this spatial location where the believers in Christ are going to go to after their death on planet Earth.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

— Yes

Notes: This specified realm of space is in heaven; the place where they often use the Yoruba word "orun" to describe. Most times, they usually talk about this place being the everlasting home for those of them who die believing in Jesus Christ.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

— Yes

Notes: Even though this religious group believes in heaven as the place for their afterlife, this place is usually in vaguely defined "above" space. They do not know the particular place where this heaven is located. What they know is that it is up there in the sky.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not have any belief in afterlife in a vaguely defined "below" space.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not have any belief in afterlife in a vaguely defined horizontal space.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not have any belief in afterlife in a vaguely defined "other" space. There is no other space apart from heaven.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not believe in the concept of reincarnation. They believe that once a person dies, such a person is bound to face judgment. In fact, it is very rare for one to see this religious group talk about anything reincarnation. Although most their members are from the Yoruba ethnic group, they do not allow the Yoruba belief in the concept of reincarnation to foreshadow their Christian belief which stipulates that judgment follows immediately after death.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There are no special treatments for adherents' corpses. Once an adherent dies, such is allowed by the family to decide on whatever will happen to the corpse.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are no co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: The group does subscribe to the practice of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: There are formal burials present in this religious group. Even though the religious group does not have a burial ground in its religious space, corpses of deceased members or relatives (with the request by the member of the group) are often buried at a stipulated place.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: The group does not build cenotaphs for corpses of deceased members.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group often bury their dead in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: If there are members with a tradition of burying their dead in the family tomb-crypt, this religious group does not do otherwise. They bury their dead following the culture of the member involved, but not one that would go against their doctrine.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: The church and the family work together to arrive at a suitable burial place for deceased members. This includes burials in domestic areas within the home.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
- Yes
- Notes: Just like many Pentecostal churches and Christians in general, this religious group believes that the supreme high god is anthropomorphic. This religious group show this through the use of different names like Alagbadaina (The one that owns a big garment of fire), Eetilukarabajere (the one that ears and answers speedily), Olugbejaomoorukan (defender of the fatherless) and so on.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
- Yes
- Notes: This religious group believes their God is a sky deity. They strongly believe that God sits in heaven and beholds on all that is being done on earth. The adherents often see their God as a God that stays up in the sky and makes the earth as his footstool.
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
- No
- Notes: This religious group does not believe that their God is chthonic (of the underworld), but one that stays in heaven. They often claim that their God uses the heaven as his home and the earth as his footstool.
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
- No
- Notes: This religious group does not believe that their God is fused with monarch (king=high god).
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
- No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
- No
- Notes: This religious group does not believe that their God is a kin relation to elites. They believe their God is the God of all flesh, both elites and commoners, and without him nothing is created.
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
- No
- Notes: This religious group believe not that their God has another type of loyalty or connection to elites. They believe their God is the God of all flesh, both elites and commoners, and without him nothing is created.
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
- Yes
- Notes: This religious group believes that God is unquestionably good no matter the evil that is happening in the world.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
- Yes [specify]: The one who created the heaven, earth, and everything for his purpose
- Notes: This religious group see their God as a loving God who rules in the affairs of all beings.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
- Yes
- Notes: This religious group maintains that their God has sufficient understanding of the world and that there is absolutely nothing that transpires on the planet earth or to humans that their God is unaware of.
- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
- No
- Notes: This religious group believes that the knowledge of their God is not restricted to any particular domain of human affairs. They believe that their God knows all things in heaven and on earth.
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not believe their God's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region. They believe that their God knows all things in heaven and on earth.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region. They believe their God knows all things in heaven and on earth, and is not restricted to only them but to all flesh.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God's knowledge is unrestricted outside the sample region. They believe their God knows all things in heaven and on earth, and is unrestricted to them alone but to all flesh.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God can see everywhere normally visible (in public). To them, there is nothing that is dark to their God; their God sees all things and places.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God can see everywhere (in the dark, at home, in the toilets and so on). To the adherents, there is no where a person is that would not be visible to their God. They have the belief that their God sees all things and places.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes the supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (including hidden motives).

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is believed by this religious group to know even the very basic character (personal essence).

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes very strongly that the supreme high god knows what will happen to its adherents, what they will do (future sight). The adherents believe all things are visible to their God.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He created the heaven, earth, and everything for his purpose

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God can reward people for whatever deeds they must have done.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes their God can punish people for any wrong done.

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No

Notes: To the adherents of this religious group, there is nothing like indirect causal efficacy in the world. If people do what is good, they will be rewarded and when they do what is evil, they will be punished.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

Notes: This religious group believes the supreme high god exhibits positive emotions. The adherents believe that whenever they praise their God in songs and worship, they are giving him what will make him happy and as such, he would be spurred into answering their prayers.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

Notes: Just like the positive emotion, the religious group also believes their God exhibits negative emotion. If they do what is bad, they believe their God is not going to be happy with them.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

Notes: This religious group usually claims the supreme high god does not possess hunger for physical food and it is only thanksgiving that is being craved by this god from his followers.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

Notes: This group does not believe their God is to be worshipped through any high god. They want their adherents to worship God by themselves and not through any intermediary.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They belief that God is the creator of heaven, earth, and everything for his purpose
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

Notes: This religious group believes that the supernatural high god communicates with them in waking, everyday life.
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

Notes: This medium is a veritable means whereby the Supreme high god communicates with the adherents of this religious group. However, it is not all members that experience this kind of interaction with the supreme being.
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

Notes: Divination in this instance is the ability of the members to inquire of the set-man of the religious group matters that can be spiritually discerned and since he is a prophet, he will tell them what the supreme being reveals to him. Also, the word "thus saith the Lord" is one that usually shows the oracular word of the supreme God towards his people in this religious group.
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

Notes: Members-alike have been seen to also communicate with the Supreme God.

- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - Notes: This religious group does not practice the monarchy system and as such, they do not have a monarch.
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This religious group believes in non-human supernatural beings like angels.
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - Notes: This religious group does not believe the supernatural beings can be seen physically, though they are believed to be seen in dreams, trances and so on.
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are believed by this religious group to see inside the heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

– I don't know

Notes: This is the reason many people are trouping en-masse into this religious group. They believe that non-human supernatural beings who manifest through their founder/prophet (Abiodun Oladele) know what will happen to them and what they will do in future.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Things in heaven and on earth, and even things to come

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Ability to serve God and to fight the forces of evil in the higher dimensions

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

Notes: To this religious group, there is nothing like mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes in or possesses a variety of supernatural beings. There is a belief in the ministry of angels.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

Notes: This religious group does not believe that the supernatural beings are organised by kinship based on a family model.

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– No

Notes: This religious group does not believe that supernatural beings are organised hierarchically.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– No

Notes: This religious group does not believe that the power of beings is domain specific.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes there is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular, which is able to promote cooperation among group members, including moral and ethical standards, contract honoring, hospitality, and emergency assistance, extending beyond moral and ethical norms to include oaths and hospitality.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group holds dearly to the taboo of sin. The group believes anything that is contrary to the Bible is a taboo for its members.

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– No

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder in whatever guise or form is highly prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions. Murder in whatever form or guise is highly prohibited and kicked against.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities. Murder is whatever form or guise is highly prohibited and kicked against.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: To this religious group, the issue of adultery is highly cared about and frowned at.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings are against incest since it has to do with sexual relations between relatives.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Bestiality, sexual immorality, perverts and so on

Notes: Since the Christian Scripture frowns at having sexual intercourse with animals, this religious group also frowns at it.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
Notes: The supernatural beings in this religious group care about shirking risk. They are believed to care about members or adherents avoiding or neglecting a duty or responsibility.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
Notes: To this group, crime is crime. The supernatural beings care about whatever crime is committed, including property crimes.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
Notes: Rituals, in this group are calendrical. When it comes to life crisis ritual, the only ritual that is being carried out is prayer. This group believes the supernatural wants them to pray without ceasing. This is the reason they pray at all times.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
Notes: Rituals, in this group are calendrical. When it comes to life crisis ritual, the only ritual that is being carried out is prayer. This group believes the supernatural wants them to pray without ceasing. This is the reason they pray at all times.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
Notes: This religious group believes in fulfilling the Biblical injunction that requests believers to go to all parts of the world and make them the disciples of Jesus Christ. Matthew 28:19-20. They believe the supernatural beings are very much interested and care about conversion of non-religionists.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
Notes: Just like every other Christian group, this religious group adheres to the Biblical injunctions of economic fairness. Passages like: "Oppressing the poor in order to enrich oneself, and giving to the rich, will lead only to loss" (Proverbs 22:16). "Do not rob the poor because they are poor, or crush the afflicted at the gate; for the Lord pleads their cause and despoils of life those who despoil them" (Proverbs 22:22-23).
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes
Notes: The supernatural beings care about the personal hygiene of this religious group. They usually hold on to the phrase (Cleanliness is next to godliness) believed to be a proverb or

aphorism that reflects the idea that being clean and maintaining personal hygiene is a virtuous and godly practice.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: The Poor and lost souls

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:
– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through the involvement of angels.
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This religious group believes that there are supernatural punishments in the afterlife.
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes
Notes: For example, the angels

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes
Notes: This is for those who must have performed well and are deemed to be righteous by the standard of the supernatural.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes in the concept of messianism. They believe Jesus Christ is their messiah and they are still expecting his second coming. They have fervent faith in the prophecy of the prophets of old (Zech. 12:10; 9:14, Isa. 27:13) and the pronouncement of Jesus Christ that in the last days, he shall come a second time to gather all that are his unto himself (Matt. 24:29-35, I Thess. 4:16, Rev. 1:7, I Cor. 15:51-55). This time, not by incarnation, but by descending and appearing in the sky. The living true Christians shall at once ascend to meet him in the sky, but the first to rise shall be the dead believers. They will thereafter reign with him for a thousand years. They, therefore, live, preach and teach that everyone should live his/her life in such a way that he/she would be qualified for this glorified ascension (Matt. 24:36-44)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The whereabouts of the messiah seems is not in doubt, since it is believed that the messiah has gone to prepare a place for the Christians (including this religious group). They hold strongly to the belief that the messiah is in heaven. However, the time of coming of the messiah (that is, the time of his return) is unknown as he is quoted to have said he would return like a thief in the night as the bible puts it.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes the messiah is very much alive and still rules in the affairs of human beings.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Just like every other Christian that believes in the Christian Holy Scripture, there is the belief that the messiah is coming in this lifetime. They usually talk about non-believers repenting because the messiah (Jesus) is coming soon.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Coming has already passed:
 - No
 - Notes: This religious group does not believe the coming of the Messiah has already passed. Up to this time, they have continued to believe that their Messiah is coming in soon in this lifetime.
- ↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:
 - No
 - Notes: This religious group does not believe their Messiah is one in a line of many past and future messiahs. They believe he (Jesus Christ) is the only Messiah and he is still coming back to rapture them to himself.
- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No
 - ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - No
 - ↳ Other purpose:
 - Yes [specify]: To rapture all those who have accepted Jesus

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The adherents are to love God and others, to share the Gospel of Jesus Christ and make disciples of all human beings. Also, they are expected to live a life of holiness and purity, to serve others, and to be good stewards of all that God has given them.
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - Notes: Only those who are true to their religious profession will experience eschaton
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ Other survival condition:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes in the concept of love and brotherhood. They seriously encourage love towards God and their neighbours as God has rightly commanded.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: This religious group emphasises on moral norms from which they believed are derived from universal principles of justice and fairness, while conventional norms apply to what are derived locally and are contingent upon rule and authority.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: There are no particular moral norms that are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: There are no specifically moral norms that are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities. Even the one that some of the adherents of this religious group do by wearing all white in line with the founder and general overseer (Apostle Abiodun Oladele)'s, it is not explicitly given. They only copy him and do what they believe is right to them.

Reference: ALUKO, Oluwasegun Peter, and Adenike Oluwabukola IREYOMI. "Colour Symbolism in a Nigerian Church: The Case of Prophet/evangelist Abiodun Oladele of the Overcomers" *Evangelical Ministries International (ori-oke Asegun)* 04, no. 11 (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2020.41102>

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
 - Yes
 - Notes: This religious group believes that whatever a human being sows, such will also reap.
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
 - No
 - Notes: There are no moral norms of good and bad that are linked in some ways to an anthropomorphic being.
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
 - No
 - Notes: This religious group does not have any specific moral norms that are linked explicitly to the commands of anthropomorphic beings.
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society
 - All individuals within contemporary world
 - All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This religious group believes in the concept of generosity / charity. It gives both its adherents and non-adherents generously. Also, it must be noted here that the adherents give this religious group both in kind and in cash.
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This religious group strongly believes in the concept of ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity. They believe that for one to be healed of any illness, they must turn away from their filthy ways and confess Jesus Christ as their lord and

personal saviour. Ritual purity is of great essence and there must be abstention from sources of impurity.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes

↳ Cooperation:
– Yes

Notes: This religious group strongly uphold the concept of cooperation among its adherents. The group is highly interested in making sure there is cooperation that will lead to unity among its adherents.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

Notes: This religious group does not believe that all is lost for any of its adherents. It believes that once anyone comes to Jesus Christ with the believe that he/she can be saved, such would be saved. It is keen on seeing that its adherents are very optimistic in knowing that all shall be well with them.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is one virtue that is strongly advocated by this religious group. If they must be healed from every disease, they must have faith/belief/trust/devotion.
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Gays, bisexuals and so on.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Bisexuals, lesbians, transgender

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require compulsory fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require forgone food opportunities like taboos on desired foods.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of adults. This is a grievous offence that is even against the constitution of the country, and anything against this is frowned upon by this religious group since it values the sanctity of human life

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of children. This is a grievous offence that is even against the constitution of the country, and anything against this is frowned upon by this religious group since it values the sanctity of human life.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require self-sacrifice. This is a grievous offence that is even against the constitution of the country, and anything against this is frowned upon by this religious group since it values the sanctity of human life.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of property/valuable items.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

— Yes

Notes: Membership in this religious group requires sacrifice of time. Members are enjoined to attend meetings or services including regular prayers that have been called and scheduled to take place in the church or any other chosen venue.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not allow physical risk taking for its membership.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Yes

Notes: The ethical precept that is required from anyone willing to be a member of this religious group is for such to accept Jesus Christ and their Lord and personal saviour.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

— No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require marginalization by out-group members.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

— Yes

Notes: It allows for members to pray, study the Bible and do all that are necessary for a Christian growth.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

—Hours: 2

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

—Yes

Notes: This religious group usually participate in large-scale rituals.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
—Number of participants: 3000

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
—Average interval [hours]: 2

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
—No
Notes: They do not follow a particular line of event. They are very dynamic in the way they go about organising their programmes.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
—No
Notes: They do not follow a particular line of event. They are very dynamic in the way they go about organising their programmes. There are no mechanisms used in ensuring that rituals are performed in a standardized way.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
—No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
—No
Notes: Members of this religious group do not consume intoxicants as part of their religious obligations.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

—No

Notes: There are no special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification and so on.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

—Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
—Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
—Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
—No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: This religious group is best characterised as a chiefdom. It is generally composed of a central community surrounded by or near a number of smaller subsidiary communities. All of the communities recognise the authority of a single kin group or individual with centralised power, dwelling in the primary community.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide any institutionalised famine relief. The group does not provide an organised effort to reduce starvation in its region any time there is famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are famine reliefs available to the adherents of this religious group through an institution other than the religious group, especially through the government, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and so on.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Though it is not every time, but this religious group usually provide poverty relief to cushion the effect of poverty among its adherents.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are poverty reliefs available to the adherents of this religious group through an institution other than the religious group, especially through the government, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), families and so on.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group provides institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm though this is not usually on a large scale but the religious group in question is actively involved in it.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm members of this religious group through an institution other than the religious group These include the government, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and so on.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group provides formal education to its adherents and others but this is just at the elementary and secondary levels.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

— No

Notes: The group's adherents do not interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

— Yes

Notes: The group's adherents usually interact with other institutional bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not provide public food storage. They do not have the wherewithal to do this.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Public food storage is provided to the adherents of this religious group by government and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) other than the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— No

Notes: This religious group does not provide water management (irrigation, flood control). They do not have the wherewithal to do this.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Water management is provided to the adherents of this religious group by the government.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not provide transportation infrastructure. They do not have the wherewithal to do this.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is provided to the adherents of this religious group by government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— Yes

Notes: This religious group levies tithes. They accept tithes from their adherents.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The government of the country levies taxes on the adherents of this religious group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

— No

Notes: This religious group does not provide an institutionalised police force. The question of an institutionalised police force is among the 68 items in the exclusive legislative list in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, on which only the Federal Government of Nigeria can legislate. No other organisation can do this.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group interact with an institutionalised police force provided by the government of the Federal Government of Nigeria. This is the only institutionalised police force permitted by the constitution of the country.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide institutionalised judges.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group interact with an institutionalised judicial system provided by the government of the Federal Government of Nigeria.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not enforce institutionalised punishment. They cannot make use of sanctions, fines, and incarceration to maintain conformity.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the type of offence the offender committed. If the offender kills and the court of law found him/her guilty and sentenced such a person the death, this will be carried out by the law enforcement agencies in charge.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised punishment of exile is not a common practice in the country.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised punishments do not often involve any punishment in which physical force is used and intended to cause some degree of pain or discomfort.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: This is an exclusive function of the government. The religious group does not have a formal legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is an exclusive function of the government. The religious group must abide and be subjected to the formal legal code as provided by the government.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not possess an institutionalised military. This is the function of the government to do.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents participate fully in the institutionalised military provided by the government.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that they are citizens of a country gives them the right to be protected by or subject to an institutionalised military provided by the government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not possess its own distinct written language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A non-religion-specific written language is available to the group's adherents through different institutions these adherents may have connection or affinity with other than the religious group in question.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group make use of a non-religion-specific written language through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a formal calendar. They make use of the Gregorian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They make use of the Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide food for themselves. They depend on the food that have been produced and taken to the market.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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